

Reflections in a Noisy World

Amazon Reviewers

Reviewed in the United States on February 4-7, 2025

Ryan Leaver [1]: This book is a look at the power of thinking, wrapped in an entertaining and clever story. The paradox with the king and the sage is both humorous and thought-provoking. It really makes you think about logic in a new way. While the book's main ideas are interesting, it sometimes feels a bit more abstract than I'd have liked, but it's still an enjoyable read. The mix of humor and philosophy keeps things light, while still making you reflect on how we think and reason. But it's worth checking out if you like stories that make you think.

ryan leaver

★★★★☆ a nice read

Reviewed in the United States on February 7, 2025

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Helpful

Report

Diane K.

★★★★★ Reflections in a Noisy World

Reviewed in the United States on February 5, 2025

Meandering Sobriety is an intriguing exploration of thought, perception, and scientific curiosity. Blending philosophy, storytelling, and research, the book invites readers into a reflective journey on the nature of thinking and knowledge. Through engaging anecdotes, including paradoxes and insights from the author's work in science, it offers food for thought in an era overwhelmed by information noise. With a light yet profound touch, this book promises moments of tranquility, humor, and intellectual stimulation—perfect for those who appreciate deep ideas wrapped in an accessible, thought-provoking package.

Helpful

Report

Matthew Rosenblum

★★★★★ Really interesting facts!

Reviewed in the United States on February 4, 2025

This was a very easy and thought-provoking read for anyone looking to take a break and learn a little "off heat" facts. I really enjoyed the story about how monkeys actually produce their own alcohol and behave

Diane K. [2]: Meandering Sobriety is an intriguing exploration of thought, perception, and scientific curiosity. Blending philosophy, storytelling, and research, the book invites readers into a reflective journey on the nature of thinking and knowledge. Through engaging anecdotes, including paradoxes and insights from the author's work in

science, it offers food for thought in an era overwhelmed by information noise. With a light yet profound touch, this book promises moments of tranquility, humor, and intellectual stimulation—perfect for those who appreciate deep ideas wrapped in an accessible, thought-provoking package.

Matthew Rosenblum [3]: This was a very easy and thought-provoking read for anyone looking to take a break and learn a little "off beat" facts. I really enjoyed the story about how monkeys actually produce their own alcohol and behave themselves better than humans after consumption! This book really has a variety of different topics including everything from AI to the importance of education. Overall, a fun read to learn something new.

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(*) *Note*: This post reprints the reviews [1-3] retrieved unedited from the Amazon page of [4].

References

[1] Leaver, R. (2025). A nice read. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2U1I9WNO2WB91/>

[2] Diane, K. (2025). Reflections in a Noisy World. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R27SBGSSSB0MQ7/>

[3] Rosenblum, M. (2025). Really interesting facts!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R10I97MGB1SR8T/>

[4] Vuong, Q. H. (2023). Meandering Sobriety. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0C2TXNX6L>